

Synthesis and biological evaluation of 4-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochlorides)

Kavita M. Heda^{*a} and Shirish P. Deshmukh^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Shri R. L. T. College of Science, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : kavitaheda25@gmail.com

^bP.G. Department of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji College, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract : A series of 4-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochloride) have been synthesized by the interaction of various 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides with *N*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride. These compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhimurium*, *K. pneumoniae*, *Ps. aeruginosa*, *A. niger* and *C. albicans*. The newly synthesized compounds have been characterized by analytical and IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Lactosyl thiocarbamides, hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride, 1,2,4-dithiazolidines, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The drug containing 1,2,4-dithiazolidines show a diverse range of pharmacological activities¹⁻³, antimicrobial^{4,5}, anti-inflammatory⁶⁻⁸, anti-HIV⁹, anti-ulcer^{10,11}, anti-cancer¹² and anti-convulsant^{13,14}. *N*-Lactosylated derivatives¹⁵⁻¹⁸ exhibits a wide range of medicinal activities such as antiviral, antidiabetic, analgesic and other significant activities. Here is reported the synthesis of several *N*-lactosylated-1,2,4-dithiazolidines by the interaction of several 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides with *N*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride. The required 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides were obtained by the interaction of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanates with various amines.

Results and discussion

Several 4-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochloride) have been prepared by the interaction of several 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (**1a-f**) with *N*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**2**) in CHCl₃. After condensation, the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky resi-

due. This residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid (**3a-f**). The product was found to be non-desulphurizable when boiled with alkaline lead acetate solution. The specific rotations were measured in chloroform. The result is summarized in Table 1. In spectrum analysis of product shows bands due to Ar. C-H, ali. C-H, C=O, C=N, C-N, C-O, C-S, stretching and ¹H NMR spectrum of product distinctly displayed signals due to aromatic protons and lactose ring protons. The Mass spectrum of product was also observed. The identities of these new *N*-lactosides have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and also IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectral studies¹⁹⁻²¹.

Experimental

All chemicals were research grade. Melting points determined are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a FT-IR Perkin-Elmer RXI (4000–450 cm⁻¹) spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR measurements were performed on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ solution with TMS as internal reference. The Mass spectra were recorded on a THERMO Finnigan LCQ Advantage max ion trap Mass spectro-

Table 1. Physical data for characterization of compounds (**3a-f**)

Reactant : <i>N</i> -Hepta- <i>O</i> -benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl- <i>S</i> -chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (2) (0.001 <i>M</i> , 1.150 g)							
1-Hepta- <i>O</i> -benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (1a-f)	Product	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	<i>R_f</i> value (Petroleum ether : acetone, 6 : 4)	$[\alpha]_D^{31}$ (c, CHCl ₃)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)	
						N	S
3-Phenyl	3a	83.00	142	0.67	-45.5 (c, 0.011)	1.80 (1.76)	2.71 (2.68)
3- <i>o</i> -Cl-Phenyl	3b	80.41	150	0.58	-72.7 (c, 0.011)	1.77 (1.73)	2.62 (2.64)
3- <i>m</i> -Cl-Phenyl	3c	89.00	147	0.76	-107.1 (c, 0.015)	1.75 (1.73)	2.68 (2.64)
3- <i>p</i> -Cl-Phenyl	3d	78.00	135	0.59	+163.6 (c, 0.011)	1.76 (1.73)	2.60 (2.64)
3- <i>o</i> -Tolyl	3e	88.33	130	0.72	+238 (c, 0.013)	1.80 (1.75)	2.71 (2.66)
3- <i>p</i> -Tolyl	3f	65.00	127	0.78	+254.5 (c, 0.011)	1.78 (1.75)	2.69 (2.66)

C and H analysis was found satisfactory in all cases.

meter. Optical rotation $[\alpha]_D^{31}$ measured on a Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter EQ-800 at 31 °C in CHCl₃. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on silica gel G and spots were visualized by iodine vapour. The compounds were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities by the disc diffusion assay method²². The compounds describe in this paper were first time synthesized by the multistep reaction protocol.

General procedure :

*Synthesis of 1-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides*²³ (**1a-f**) :

1-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-aryl thiocarbamides (**1a-f**) were synthesized by interaction of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanate with different amines in benzene medium.

Synthesis of N-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**2**) :

N-Hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**2**) was prepared by passing a calculated amount of chlorine through a chloroformic solution of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanate maintaining the temperature below 10 °C.

Synthesis of 4-aryl-5-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochloride) :

A mixture of 1-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-3-phenyl

thiocarbamide (**1a**, 0.001 *M*, 1.204 g in 20 ml CHCl₃) and *N*-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**2**) (0.001 *M*, 1.150 g, in 5 ml CHCl₃) was gently refluxed for 3 h. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction, the reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and the solvent removed under reduced pressure to obtain residue. This residue was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a pale yellow solid (**3a**).

(3a) IR (KBr) : ν 3062 (Ar. C-H), 2958 (Ali. C-H), 1730 (C=O), 1539 (C=N), 1315 (C-O), 1026, 908 (lactosyl ring deformation), 709 (C-S), 474 (S-S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ in ppm, CDCl₃) : 8.13–7.16 (75H, m, 14-COC₆H₅, C₆H₅), 6.74–3.75 (28H, m, lactose ring protons); Mass (*m/z*) : 2386 (M⁺) (not located), 1333 (M⁺-C₆₁H₄₉O₁₇), 1053 (HBL⁺), 948 (HBL⁺-C₇H₅O), 932 (HBL⁺-C₇H₅O₂), 918 (HBL⁺-C₈H₇O₂), 579 (TBG⁺), 458 (TBG⁺-C₇H₅O₂), 335 (TBG⁺-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO) (Found : C, 65.44; H, 4.35; N, 1.80; S, 2.71. Calcd. for C₁₃₀H₁₀₃O₃₄N₃S₂·2HCl. Required : C, 65.38; H, 4.31; N, 1.76; S, 2.68%).

(3b) IR (KBr); ν 3062 (Ar. C-H), 2958 (Ali. C-H), 1730 (C=O), 1583 (C=N), 1269 (C-O), 1026, 910 (lactosyl ring deformation), 709 (C-S), 418 (S-S) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ in ppm, CDCl₃) : 8.08–7.18 (74H, m, 14-COC₆H₅, C₆H₄), 6.75–3.72 (28H, m, lactose ring pro-

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where OBz = COC_6H_5 (benzoyl) : R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *p*-tolyl.

tons); Mass (*m/z*) : 2420.5 (M^+) (not located), 1367.5 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_{61}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_{17}$), 1126 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_{69}\text{H}_{53}\text{O}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$), 1053 (HBL^+), 948 ($\text{HBL}^+ - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBL}^+ - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 579 (TBG^+), 475 ($\text{TBG}^+ - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 335 ($\text{TBG}^+ - \text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$) (Found : C, 64.48; H, 4.25; N, 1.77; S, 2.70. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{130}\text{H}_{102}\text{O}_{34}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{HCl}$. Required : C, 64.44; H, 4.21; N, 1.73; S, 2.64%).

(3e) IR (KBr) : ν 3062 (Ar. C-H), 2976 (Ali. C-H), 1730 (C=O), 1583 (C=N), 1390 (C-O), 1026, 910 (lactosyl ring deformation), 707 (C-S), 509 (S-S) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (δ in ppm, CDCl_3) : 8.08–7.18 (74H, m, 14-

COC_6H_5 , C_6H_4), 6.74–3.72 (28H, m, lactose ring protons), 2.45–2.16 (3H, s, Ali. CH_3); Mass (*m/z*) : 2400 (M^+) (not located), 1347 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_{61}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_{17}$), 1053 (HBL^+), 948 ($\text{HBL}^+ - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 932 ($\text{HBL}^+ - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2$), 579 (TBG^+), 475 ($\text{TBG}^+ - \text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}$), 335 ($\text{TBG}^+ - \text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$), 105 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CO}$) (Found : C, 66.1; H, 4.40; N, 1.80; S, 2.71. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{131}\text{H}_{105}\text{O}_{34}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HCl}$. Required : C, 66.5; H, 4.37; N, 1.75; S, 2.66%).

Antimicrobial activity :

All the compounds have been screened for both anti-bacterial and antifungal activity by using disc diffusion

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of 4-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-3-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (hydrochloride)

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>Ps. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>K. pneumonie</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
A	12	16	10	14	16	16	19	18
B	10	17	9	11	14	–	20	16
C	11	12	11	15	12	11	–	21
D	15	13	18	11	18	12	11	9
E	12	–	13	13	12	13	17	16
F	16	10	15	–	19	15	19	20
DMSO	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Amikacin	18	21	23	19	20	21	–	–
Fluconazole	–	–	–	–	–	–	24	24

Zone size was interpreted by

Sample	Disc content	Resistant	Intermediate	Sensitive
Amikacin	100 ug/ml	≤ 15 mm	16–20 mm	≥ 21 mm
Fluconazole	100 ug/ml	≤ 15 mm	16–20 mm	≥ 21 mm

assay. For this sterile filter paper disc (6 mm) impregnated with fixed doses of compounds was placed on pre-inoculated surface. The disc bearing plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. Inhibition zones read after incubation at 37 °C for 24 h for bacterial strains and for fungal strains inhibition zones read after incubation at 35 °C for 48 h. The compounds were taken at a concentration of 1 mg/ml using dimethyl sulphoxide as a solvent. Amikacin (100 µg/ml) was used as standard for antibacterial and Fluconazole (100 µg/ml) as a standard for antifungal activity. The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in nutrient agar medium and for *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* in potato dextrose agar medium. It has been observed that all the compounds showed nearly same activity against both bacteria and fungi. **3d** and **3f** exhibits most significant activity against *Salmonella typhi*. **3b** exhibits good activity against *S. aureus*. The compounds **3a**, **3b** and **3f** showed good activity against *A. niger* while compounds **3c** and **3f** showed good activity against *C. albicans*. All other compounds exhibited low to moderate activity.

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